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The Aesthetics of Unreliability: Creativity, Criticism and Artistic Judgement

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Abstract

This essay examines the role of unreliability as a constitutive condition of artistic creation rather than merely a defect of interpretation or judgement. Beginning with the familiar claim that a work of art should be allowed to "speak for itself," it questions the authority traditionally accorded to critics and explores the complex relationship between artistic intention, critical mediation and audience reception. Drawing upon Kevill Melchionne's conception of the "Aesthetics of Unreliability" and Yuriko Saito's theory of everyday aesthetics, the essay argues that aesthetic judgement is necessarily provisional, situated and corrigible. It proposes a distinction between *defendable* judgement, which can be justified through reasons, and *dependable* judgement, which acquires credibility through repeated practice, revision and responsiveness to materials, experience and critique.

The discussion further examines how unreliability functions as a productive force in creative practice by fostering experimentation, innovation and interpretive openness. Examples drawn from literature, cinema, music and the visual arts—including unreliable narration, fragmented storytelling, improvisation, chance operations, Wabi-Sabi aesthetics and the creative use of accident—demonstrate that uncertainty frequently becomes an enabling rather than disabling condition of artistic expression. Rather than treating unreliability as a failure to attain certainty, the essay proposes it as a dynamic mode of aesthetic engagement through which artists, critics and audiences continually renegotiate meaning. Artistic authority, it concludes, is neither absolute nor self-validating; it remains local, provisional and sustained through an ongoing dialogue between creation, interpretation and lived experience.

Keywords: aesthetics of unreliability; artistic judgement; creativity; everyday aesthetics; art criticism; unreliable narration; interpretation; creativity studies; Wabi-Sabi; artistic authority.

1. Can Art Speak for Itself?

It has not been uncommon to hear the statements such as "let the work speak for herself!" It is often found that many creators do not want any sort of 'mediation,' because critics often misdescribe what the work is doing, or what it intends to convey. This happens either because the critics impose a framework that is alien to the tradition within which a creation had been

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conceived, or the critics might have misdescribed the work of art. The verbal description of what a visual or audio text is to be understood as often fall flat because critics often mediate attention that flatten one's experience of reading, viewing or listening to. The critics may think they are the arbiters of taste, but this view is seriously contested by the likes of Kevill Melchionne (1995) who would advocate for the concept of 'Aesthetics of Unreliability.'

Literature offers perhaps the clearest illustration of use of unreliability. The technique of the unreliable narrator does not merely conceal information from the reader; it invites readers to participate in constructing meaning. In William Faulkner's *The Sound and the Fury* (1929/1990), the fractured consciousness of successive narrators prevents the emergence of a single, authoritative account of reality. Vladimir Nabokov's *Lolita* (1955/1997) compels readers to recognise the gap between persuasive rhetoric and moral truth, while Ryūnosuke Akutagawa's *In a Grove* (1915-22/2000), later immortalised in Akira Kurosawa's 1950-film *Rashomon*, constructs an entire narrative out of mutually contradictory testimonies. These works do not ask the reader to discover which version is objectively true. Instead, they transform uncertainty itself into an aesthetic experience. Reliability here is replaced by interpretive participation.

Although it begins as a literary strategy in most cases, Cinema today makes good use of this strategy. That is why, we notice that films such as Akira Kurosawa's *Rashomon* (1950), Christopher Nolan's *Memento* (2000), David Lynch's *Mulholland Drive* (2001), or Sriram Raghavan's *Andhadhun* (2018) makes a conscious attempt to unsettle the spectator's confidence in perception, memory and causality. They do not portray a stable world. In contrast, they invite audiences to decide and negotiate between competing realities. Because of this approach, we find the spectator becoming less a consumer of meaning here. The viewers also become a collaborator in the production of these visual texts. The resulting uncertainty is not a defect in cinematic storytelling. I would argue that this is exactly its most powerful expressive resources.

If we pursue this approach further in the fields of painting, we notice that visual art can also show productive unreliability in the work of many artists. An artist such as J. M. W. Turner (1775-1851) conceived about playing with this uncertainty when he decided to work further on concrete topography to dissolve the images or its form into what can be called an experiential atmosphere. We see in his later day works use of vapor, colour and swirling light, which would leave viewers suspended between recognition and abstraction. He also played with the way one would like to have proportions of painted canvas with a 70/30 rule, where all the surprises would come in the 30 per cent 'unknown.' An abstract expressionist painter such as Jackson Pollock's (1912-1956) drip paintings would serve as another example. He decided to deviate from the traditional style of painting on canvas. He placed canvases on his studio floor and used stiff brushes, towels and sticks to drop and drip household paints and thinned enamels on the canvas. The result of this uncertain method, which is also a kind of accidental style, resulted in some compositional principles unknown so far. The Japanese *kintsugi* art technique is the third instance where broken pottery parts are joined without hiding their damages to finally turn the ceramic vessels into visible lines of beauty. They use lacquer mixed with powdered gold to repair them. The repaired object acquires a richer identity precisely because its history of breakage remains visible. Here, imperfection is not something to be hidden but is a part of artistic strategy to reveal it to the viewers.

Music could also take us to several such striking examples. The work of American composer and music theorist, John Cage (1912-1992) serves as a case. His use of non-standard instruments to create music out of them, and his incorporation of chance operations into

composition, and finally, his treatment of ‘unpredictability’ not as an interference but as a compositional material made his scores unusual. It is said that many of his unusual sounds came from the South Asian and Eastern cultures, especially from the Zen Buddhist musical sources. Jazz improvisation similarly depends upon uncertainty. Every performance unfolds through attentive listening, spontaneous response and negotiated risk. The musicians trust neither rigid scores nor complete randomness; they rely instead upon cultivated judgement exercised under constantly changing circumstances. The performance succeeds not because uncertainty has been eliminated but because it has been transformed into disciplined creativity. A number of Jazz musicians show this trend but the most prominent among them seems to be Miles Davis (1926-1991) who gave his musicians only a skeletal score while finally recording his album ‘*Kind of Blue*’ (1959) from Columbia Records. The pianist involved in its production, Bill Evans (1929-1980) described that the musicians received a minimum set of instructions and a few scales only. What emerged was mostly through attentive listening and responding to extempore. While such ‘real-time’ conversations, known as ‘*Sawāl-Jawāb*’ (literally meaning, ‘Questions and answers’) in the duets performed by instrumental musicians in both *Karnātaki* and North Indian tradition of music in India are common in musical performances. This kind of uncertainty is both expected and appreciated by listeners. This is perhaps very surprising for the western composers.

2. The Critic as Mediator, Not Arbiter

In the Indian tradition, the critic is the one who often extends the original treatise or text, by offering very copious arguments for and against, often known as ‘*Ṭīkā*’ (referring to commentary or glossing) or ‘*Bhāṣya*’ (standing for extensive expositions). Good art criticism often complements the original work. It brings attention of viewers to the creative uncertainty and ingenuity of the author or the artist. Criticism is not a filter but a way of understanding the work. Many critics often take it as if they have an unjustified authority to negatively speak about the text they are called upon to comment. Just as translators and interpreters extend and expand a literary work to make it relevant and appreciable in another culture, a critic is also expected to expand the artist’s work but using a different medium – the verbal medium. Even when viewers arrive to see a work of art, or an exhibition, there may not be any guarantee of neutrality. The viewers coming to an art exhibition may also arrive with a cultural script in their mind. They are usually guided by market expectations or what is called a trend in social media. Their expectation and attention could also have been influenced in a way. They could go by their viewing habit or could have had an institutional framing. On the other hand, it shows some degree of reliability when one sees that the critical review is trying to open up new perceptual possibilities or assign new meanings to a creative text. At times, they help the viewers or audiences notice some non-obvious features, without passing a verdict or a judgement. Their observations come from practice of viewing many visual texts, even though the best critics also know about the existence of multiple ways of opening a review. The reviews are a provisional understanding of an art-work – often, an experiment in understanding and interpreting. The failure of a critic becomes evident where they claim authority over artists and announce a sort of finality over meaning. Whenever such negative criticism seem biased, or when it fails, the artists often feel that there has been a ‘theft’ of authority here, or a dilution of intent. I would not be surprised if the artists feel threatened when they face with such biased or hostile reviews.

3. Everyday Aesthetics and the Limits of Interpretation

Reviewers and critics are there to study an art form or help understand a text – visual or verbal. They do not exist because either the artists or the audiences need them. They thrive (and survive) because artists often are not so expressive about their tools or techniques, or aesthetic experiments. They extend immediate articulation, and each society invents roles to wrestle with that excess. In the digital age, many platforms have created ways of audiences directly letting the artists know their reactions but the audience response there can only indicate likes and dislikes, or successes and failures, or very brief comments – but never go into intricacies or nuances, or causes behind a creative piece or the methods employed by the creator. In fact, it is now learned in the hard way that aggregation is not a careful articulation. Experience of trying to capture what is visually constructed into what is verbally describable may outrun the existing vocabulary. A critical review cannot guarantee a ‘correct’ interpretation as such. In fact, some may even declare that there are no ‘the’ correct interpretations. With the explosion of art objects, from being a rarity to becoming a matter of everyday aesthetics, following artists such as Yuriko Saito (2007), there has been an interesting development. Saito and others would argue that we have always overlooked the potential of the art of the mundane, the boundary between the ordinary and the extra-ordinary is now breaking down.

The world of art had been dominated by ‘rare objects’, ‘artworks’, which attract the market because of their novelty and unavailability, and because the art critics often raise the expectations by bringing in comparisons that untrained eyes were not used to remember or recall. But everyday aesthetics brings in smells, soundscapes, street-food, clothing and habitation as the focus of attention.

4. Can Artists Trust Their Own Judgement?

All these discussions make one think if an artist can rely on her own judgement. Would the opinion of the artist about her own art and craft always prove to be defensible and dependable? The intuition would say that artists do and must rely on their own judgement, or else they would not be able to create. However, that judgement cannot be an absolute, and once-and-for-all kind of opinion, as they do not have a guarantee from anyone to be always right. And this thin degree of uncertainty is not a weakness of art; on the contrary, it is one of its working conditions. This position has to be unpacked with care and caution. One knows that the artist’s judgment is indispensable but it cannot be self-certifying. From the choices of form or framework or themes or treatments, or in visualising about the risks and exclusions, there cannot be any artist who would seriously think: “If I judge it right, it must be right.” If one did, it would only show that their confidence is misplaced. Relying on oneself would mean that the artist has *sufficient* trust to act, *readiness* to revise, and is making a *provisional* commitment to what she is doing. Artists judge under conditions that maximize unreliability, as they know they are not infallible. They also have this difficulty in re-experiencing the work as a stranger, as they are deeply immersed in their act.

5. Reliability, Dependability and Creative Judgement

It is not surprising to find that many of them put their work away for a period, or change scale or medium, and even get their work photographed to show the draft to others to seek their opinion. These go by the name of a kind of ritual which can be called *manufacture distance*: These are actually ‘reliability checks.’ When the artists feel they have a judgement about themselves (or about their art and craft in general), they may have a defensible judgement.

Such judgements can be articulated where reasons and decisions can be explained. These judgements are also dependable because their judgment may continue to work across cases, can get better with all future decisions, and can even survive stress, change, and critique. They may defend at a given point of time, faced with criticism, against unfavourable reviews, but they can become 'dependable' over time. This dependability is not logical – it's *earned* through repetition, failure, course correction, and responsive to resistance (from materials, viewers, constraints).

6. Creativity under Conditions of Unreliability

Let us go into some details of how the concept of 'Unreliability' is related to the issue of 'Creativity'. Unreliability and the insatiable hunger for more are powerful, dual-edged drivers of creativity. They create the psychological tension and instability that often force the brain to 'innovate.' Whether it refers to an unpredictable environment, unstable mood, or inconsistent habits, 'Unreliability' forces creative adaptation. In the process, it helps break the monotony and the routine. Predictable routines kill creative thinking. Unreliability forces one to come out of comfort zones. Secondly, it sparks what we can call 'Crisis Innovation.' When systems or people fail, your brain must find immediate, alternative solutions. The idiom such as 'Necessity is the mother of invention' emerged because of these situations. It also enhances deviant and divergent thought processes. We have seen that chaotic inputs force the brain to connect unrelated ideas to survive. Further, they create an emotional friction – which affects the mood. It is this mood instability that provides a deep well of intense, raw material for artistic expression. It is a different matter that chronic unreliability causes burnout, stress, and prevents the execution of long-term plans.

In comparison, the 'hunger for more,' often known as possessing ambition, curiosity, or chronic dissatisfaction – they all act as the ultimate fuel for creative output. First, it prevents complacency, because in that case, reaching a goal is never enough. This pushes you to experiment with new styles or mediums. The insatiability drives 'Obsessive Mastery,' as the desire to improve forces deep focus and thousands of hours of deliberate practice. This is also when we learn to take risks, because the standard methods feel boring. The hunger for novelty makes you try bold, unproven concepts, resulting in high outputs. A restless mind produces more work, increasing the odds of a masterpiece. The only downside is that it can lead to toxic perfectionism, where one never finishes or appreciates one's own works.

7. Creative Practices of Unreliability

When these two forces combine, they create a chaotic but highly fertile ground for genius. Unreliability provides the unpredictable sparks and raw emotional data, while the hunger for more provides the obsessive drive to shape that chaos into something tangible. The issue is how does one weaponize unpredictability in one's workflow, narrative structures, or artistic philosophy. First, one can use it in building 'Narratives' and in 'Storytelling.' One can, in fact, move beyond plain lying. Some of the greatest literary works derive their power from unreliable narration. In *The Sound and the Fury*, the fragmented consciousness of Benjy and Quentin prevents readers from receiving a stable account of events; meaning emerges only by reconstructing conflicting perspectives. Similarly, *Lolita* compels readers to distrust Humbert Humbert's eloquent self-justifications, forcing them to distinguish between narration and moral reality. In Japanese literature, *In a Grove* presents contradictory testimonies of the same incident, making uncertainty itself the central aesthetic experience rather than a flaw in storytelling. Four different viewpoints in Satinath Bhaduri's *Jagari* can be cited as yet another

example. In Tagore's *Ghare Baire*, the alternating first-person narratives of Nikhilesh, Sandip and Bimala expose the impossibility of reducing political or emotional truth to a single perspective. The novel's authority lies precisely in its refusal to privilege one voice over another.

A multi-layered unreliable narrator who is unreliable due to memory gaps, severe bias, or cognitive dissonance, can help the readers or viewers to see the same event from three different viewpoints. Let the audience piece together the truth from the contradictions. This would be the strategy of shifting perspectives. The film makers often create unreliable environments, by designing sets where physics, time, or geography shift unpredictably to mirror a character's internal chaos. It could be a curious mix of illusions and delusions. Secondly, one can make use of a controlled chaos in the Creative Process. One can introduce random constraints. One can use tools like Brian Eno's *Oblique Strategies* cards, where you are forced to execute random, unexpected instructions mid-project. Thirdly, one can incorporate what is known as 'Glitch Art,' i.e. intentionally use broken tools, corrupted files, or malfunctioning software to find unique aesthetic patterns. Finally, one can also deconstruct routine changes in one's workspace, work hours, or creative mediums weekly to shock the participants' brain out of comfort.

Music provides equally compelling examples of controlled chaos. Composer John Cage incorporated chance operations into composition, treating unpredictability not as interference but as a compositional principle. Similarly, the improvisational traditions of jazz rely upon uncertainty, where musicians continually negotiate unexpected responses to create performances that cannot be exactly repeated.

Cinema has repeatedly transformed unreliability into an artistic device. *Rashomon* presents mutually incompatible versions of the same event, denying viewers the comfort of a single authoritative truth. *Memento* reconstructs narrative through the memory deficits of its protagonist, while *Mulholland Drive* blurs the boundaries between dream, fantasy and reality. Rather than confusing audiences, these films demonstrate that uncertainty can become a method for deeper engagement, compelling viewers to become active interpreters rather than passive recipients. Contemporary Indian cinema increasingly explores unreliable perception. *Talvar* reconstructs the same crime through competing investigative narratives, while *Andhadhun* repeatedly destabilises what viewers believe they have witnessed. These films illustrate that ambiguity can generate ethical reflection rather than mere suspense.

In Conceptual Philosophy, the beauty of imperfection (or, *Wabi-Sabi* in Japanese philosophy) becomes important as we are willing to accept transience and imperfection. Some creative persons highlight the flaws in their work rather than fixing them. Some create art that is inherently unreliable and temporary, what could be called 'ephemeral,' such as ice sculptures, sand art, or street performances prone to weather disruption. Use the unreliability as a Psychological Tool to do subconscious mining which works like this: (a) Capture ideas immediately upon waking; (b) Write down your dreams, or (c) Make a note when exhausted. Our brain's logical filters are weak during these unreliable states, letting raw creativity through. We could also treat unpredictable mood swings not as a barrier, but as a rotating palette of different creative lenses.

The visual arts equally celebrate productive unreliability. The late paintings of J. M. W. Turner dissolve solid forms into uncertain atmospheres, allowing ambiguity to become expressive rather than defective. The drip paintings of Jackson Pollock deliberately incorporate accident

and gesture, while the practice of Kintsugi transforms fracture itself into aesthetic value. In each case, apparent imperfection becomes an indispensable element of artistic meaning.

8. The Paradox of Artistic Authority

When Melchionne or painter-philosophers such as Yuriko Saito (*Everyday Aesthetics*, OUP 2007) talk about ‘Everyday Aesthetics,’ they are turning it inward. Artists don’t judge their art or their colleagues’ creativity from a distance. They operate in fatigue, distraction, mood, constraint, and several other problems such as practical deadlines. Therefore, the judgment is reliable *enough* to guide action, but not to settle value. It is not surprising that the great writers or artists disown their works later. But that does not retroactively invalidate the earlier judgment.

The artists still need “others,” not necessarily the arbiters, because if self-judgment were dependable in isolation, there would be no need for peer feedback, critical introduction, editorial comments, or audiences. When such evaluations pile up, they will still not replace the artist’s judgment. They would, however, try and **perturb it**, as the critique would introduce elements of surprise, and alternative salience – to which there may be some resistance from the artist. This perturbation is not about authority—it’s about *de-habitation*.

This leads us to an interesting paradox of artistic (or authorial) authority. The tension is because the artist is the *only one* who can make certain decisions, about the art object or design or product, and at the same time, the artist may also be *the worst positioned* to finalize their value. That is why the artistic authority is always local, provisional and also revocable (sometimes by the artist herself). The artistic confidence and artistic humility are not opposites—they’re co-requirements.

An artist’s judgment is not dependable because it is private, nor defensible because it is sincere. It becomes dependable insofar as it:

- stays responsive to materials and effects
- remains corrigible by experience
- can survive reinterpretation without collapsing

That’s not something you *have*. It’s something you *maintain*. An artist can rely on her own judgment—but only as one relies on a compass in bad weather. Demanding absolute dependability would paralyze creation. Dismissing self-judgment would outsource art to committees. Art lives in the tension.

9. Conclusion: Living with Unreliability

To conclude, one could summarise the lessons we have learned from the practical use of ‘Unreliability’ in the fields of creative writing, painting and film making. If unreliability is accepted as one of the working conditions of creativity rather than an obstacle to it, then its presence can be observed across artistic traditions. The history of art repeatedly demonstrates that uncertainty, incompleteness and the refusal of singular authority are not signs of failure but methods through which creative works acquire depth and longevity. Artists frequently discover that meaning is not exhausted at the moment of creation; it emerges through successive acts of interpretation, revision and reception.

The same principle appears in everyday creative practices. Street performances, temporary installations, sand sculptures, rangoli designs, seasonal decorations, culinary traditions and craft practices all acknowledge transience as an intrinsic feature of aesthetic experience. As Yuriko Saito has argued in her work on everyday aesthetics, artistic value often resides not in permanence but in attentive engagement with ordinary life. The work exists for a particular moment, within particular circumstances, and derives meaning from that situated encounter rather than from timeless preservation.

The examples given in the earlier sections of this paper suggest that unreliability should not be understood merely as epistemic uncertainty or interpretive instability. It is equally a practical discipline. Creative work requires the courage to make decisions without complete certainty, the humility to revise those decisions, and the wisdom to recognise that no work ever arrives at a final or exhaustive meaning. The artist's confidence therefore coexists with self-doubt, just as innovation coexists with failure. The very practices through which artists seek distance from their own work—drafts, rehearsals, workshops, peer critique, editorial intervention and repeated revision—are not admissions of weakness but mechanisms for cultivating dependable judgement.

Perhaps this explains why enduring works of art continue to invite fresh interpretations long after their creators have disappeared. Their strength lies not in having closed the space of meaning but in having preserved it. They remain reliable not because they dictate a single interpretation but because they continue to sustain new acts of understanding across generations. Their apparent unreliability is, paradoxically, the source of their permanence.

Seen in this light, the aesthetics of unreliability is neither a celebration of confusion nor a rejection of artistic judgement. It is an acknowledgement that creativity flourishes in the space between certainty and openness. The artist relies upon experience, intuition and craft, yet remains willing to have each of these tested by materials, audiences and time. Every artistic decision is therefore provisional, not because it is arbitrary, but because it remains responsive to future experience.

One might therefore conclude that the artist can rely upon her own judgement only in the way that a seasoned navigator relies upon a compass during uncertain weather. The compass does not eliminate storms, nor does it guarantee arrival. It merely provides a dependable orientation amid changing conditions. Likewise, artistic judgement offers direction without claiming infallibility. It remains trustworthy precisely because it is corrigible, because it welcomes reinterpretation, and because it accepts that meaning is never wholly possessed by either the creator or the critic.

Art, then, survives not by overcoming unreliability but by inhabiting it. Creativity is sustained by the continual negotiation between conviction and doubt, intention and reception, permanence and change. The work of art speaks most powerfully not when it silences alternative readings, but when it continues to generate them. In that continuing dialogue between artist, artwork and audience lies the enduring vitality of aesthetic experience.

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